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CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Electronic Customer Relationship Management (ECRM) has become the latest paradigm in the world of Customer Relationship Management. ECRM is more necessary in businesses as a part of web. The web-enabled companies can no longer rely on traditional bricks or mortar strategies in the current situation. Such organizations have to evolve with the market instead of behind it. This paper explains the value of ECRM, its benefits, outlines the focal points to address prior to implementation, outlines potential pitfalls during implementation and to describe the ways to avoid which takes a look at recent trends and presents a proven ECRM success story.

Key-Words: - ECRM, Customer Relationship Management, Loyalty, Brand.

1. Introduction

All organizations involved in on-line business to business and/or business to consumer selling need to educate themselves about the new phenomenon of Electronic Customer Relationship Management (ECRM). According to Romano (2001), ECRM is concerned with attracting and keeping economically valuable customers and eliminating less profitable ones. Romano and Fjermestad (2002) are convinced that ECRM will develop important area of study in Management Information System and disciplines such as Computer Science and Marketing Psychology. A study was made by Boston Consulting Group which shows the result that 65% of on-line customers who purchase at a given web -site will never like to make a second purchase. These facts should be a wake-up call to web-enabled companies that there is a real service gap to address and that additional profits await those companies who quickly find a way to fill this gap. ECRM can help companies meet this challenge. The trend of shopping on-line may bring customers in through the online door, but what keeps them coming back through that same door is the overall quality of the customer experience. Organizations doing business online need to understand this, because the cost of marketing to an existing customer is \$6.80 over the Internet versus \$34.00 to attain a new web customer (Karpinski,2001). In addition, Keen (in Greenberg, 2001) predicts that the share of business-to-business marketplaces using ECRM solutions will grow from 3% in 1999 to more than 50% in 2004 and currently it is above 60%. Investing in ECRM solutions will benefit companies the tools which is required to create, maintain and provide competitive advantage in the market.

ECRM BENEFITS

A recent study revealed that a 10% gain in repeat customers can add about 10% to the company's profits. On the other hand, a 10% reduction in the total marketing expenditures needed to attract new visitors adds only .7% to the bottom line. As a whole, keeping existing customers satisfied is more profitable than going after greater numbers of new customers, even when a company is able to trim down the cost of attracting those new potential customers. The best way to keep these existing customers satisfied is to deliver value to them on their own terms.[3] The following objectives can be achieved with a proper ECRM implementation (increased customer loyalty, attractive and effective marketing, enhanced customer service and support and greater competence and cost cutback)

Increased customer loyalty

An effective ECRM system lets a company communicate with its customers using a single and consistent voice, regardless of the communication channel. This is because, with ECRM software, everyone in an organization has access to the same transaction history and information about the customer. Information captured by an ECRM system helps a company to identify the actual costs of winning and retaining individual customers. Having this data allows the firm to focus its time and resources on its most profitable customers. One tool that a company can implement in pursuit of customer loyalty is personalization. Personalization software tools generate real-time profiles for each customer using data from many sources including customer databases, clickstream data and transaction systems.[2] Personalization is more effective on business-to-business sites. Personalization contains two types software

Rules-based personalization software which allows direct control of the type of sites shown to users. Companies structure the rules to reduce the volume of available information down to palatable level and it is hard to scale because rules require manual updating.

Collaborative filtering personalization software inspires browsing of sites and choices based on personal taste. For example, Amazon.com and snapdeal.com shows purchasers of particular items sets of related items that other shoppers with similar shopping patterns have purchased. This act encourages increased sales activity and also adds value for the customer by presenting items that they may not have known would interest them.

More effective marketing

Having detailed customer information from an ECRM system allows a company to predict the kind of products that a customer is likely to buy as well as the timing of purchases. In the short term, this information helps an organization create more effective and focused marketing/sales campaigns. ECRM allows for more targeted campaigns and tracking of campaign effectiveness. Customer data can be analyzed from multiple perspectives to discover which elements of a marketing campaign had the greatest impact on sales and profitability. In addition, customer segmentation can improve marketing efforts.[3]

Improved customer service and support

An ECRM system provides a single repository of customer information. This enables a company to serve customer needs quickly and efficiently. ECRM-enabling technologies include search engines, live help, e-mail management, news feeds/content management and multi-language support. Two key ways are used to improve customer service and provide support through e-mail and direct mail campaigns. A robust bulk e-mail management tool can help get offers to a wide range of prospective customers and can customize how that offer is presented. The direct mail approaches have much better results. The right tools facilitate sending the right offers to the right customers. An additional way to assist customers is through improved call center interaction. When customers dial in to a call center, they expect superior service and timely response.[2] ECRM call center technology helps manage call routing and tracking facility. Service representatives are quickly provided with the information they need to troubleshoot and solve problems.

Greater efficiency and cost reduction

Integrating customer data into a single database allows marketing teams, sales forces, and other departments within a company to share information. Example: Identifying unproductive/underutilized resources, closer tracking of costs, better forecasting for the pipeline and setting realistic project metrics and measurements to quantify return on investment.

ECRM CONSIDERATION

ECRM plan for implementation only when there is need for companies. The following points are considered during implementation phase:

Developing customer focused business strategies

The objective of this step is not to try to mold the customer to the company's goals but to listen to the customer and try to create opportunities beneficial to each. It is important to offer customers their current needs and the future demands. This can be achieved by providing a variety of existing access channels for customers, such as e-mail, telephone and fax, and by preparing to provide for future access channels such as wireless communication.

Retooling business functions

Starting to do business via ECRM will require organizational change in order to determine which departments/functions are truly servicing the customer and which ones are only adding to overhead. After identifying and trimming redundant headcount, administrative time and cost should drop. Positive organizational change will not simply materialize on its own. It is the responsibility of senior management to ensure that all employees understand the necessity of the changes, how the new structure will benefit them, and how it will enhance their ability to serve their customers. Senior management must stress that ECRM itself is only a tool.[2]

Work process re-engineering

The departmental role and responsibility changes from retooling business functions for adopting new work processes. The choices here are to take the traditional step-wise approach or an integrated one toward improving work efficiency. Under the step-wise approach, departments are treated as separate efficiency entities and they rarely produce good results because the goals of each department can become too parochial. In the integrated approach it tends to produce superior results because it recognizes the interdependencies among the company's multiple functions/departments and how these create the larger perspective of the entire organization.

Technology choices

The technology choices mainly depends on the industry and their position. ECRM are the good candidates for company in implementation. Criteria for technology choices include:

- scalability of software
- tool set flexibility for customization
- stability of the existing ECRM application code
- compatibility of ECRM application with legacy and Internet systems
- level of technical support available during and after implementation
- upgradable support
- availability of additional modules
- security

Providing security to one's company and customers is becoming an ever more important aspect of customer service. There are two types of security that an organization should address. The first type is security from a company perspective. A recent study by the Boston-based company Meridien Research indicated that the rising rate of Internet fraud could be slashed by an amazing two thirds if e-businesses were to adopt currently available authentication and fraud-detection technologies. This could save such companies nearly over years.[2] Clearly, it is in a company's best interest to protect itself from such infringements. Organizations should

consider setting up flags in the security software that will be tripped when the number of transactions or dollar. The second type of security is focused on one's customers. Customer focused security deals with steps that a company should take to inspire trust from its customers that their on-line transactions are secure. Through the use of authentication, or automated clearinghouse, , the risk of customer fraud is greatly reduced. Authentication is a process used to confirm the user's identity. This can be accomplished with user ids and passwords.

Training and preparation

Training and preparation is the most important one in ECRM implementation. Depending on the number of users, training times will vary from company to company. Training of employees should occur before the new ECRM system has been implemented to ensure a seamless transition for customers.[3] Examples of training include sending users to training facilities at considerable cost or bringing in an on-site consultant. Anyone who requires access to the system should receive full, appropriate and timely training. Training should be an ongoing, managed activity as systems must continuously change and evolve. All training and tools used should be thoroughly documented for current, new and future employees. Without a documentation management scheme, the value of the ECRM system will degrade rapidly.

ECRM PITFALLS

In a typical CRM implementation, 28% of the total cost goes to buying software, and 38% of the cost goes to services such as software customizations, application integration and training. However, Hardware makes up 23% of the cost, while telecommunications expenses make up the remaining 11%. In order to justify the millions of dollars needed to successfully implement a CRM system, the firm's decision-makers must identify and define their corporate strategy in order to see positive returns for their investment. The following list outlines the pitfalls and how to avoid them:

- Mismatch between a company and the vendor's CRM software. Every effort must be made to find a vendor whose product is flexible enough to the company's best practices and does not force the company to adopt the vendor's best practices. Each company should select the solution that handles the critical customer-facing functions and maintains robust links to the existing ERP system.
- A poor understanding of the company's business processes. Each of the business processes should be reviewed, analyzed and documented before shopping for a vendor.
- ECRM implementations that take more than 90 days have a high failure rate. A company should be belief about implementations that are considerably longer than the 90 days.
- Vendor stability should be a criteria used in selection. Check the financial stability of the vendor to assess whether or not it is likely to be able to survive a softening economy.
- Rejection by end users is always is a possibility when business functions are retooled. If the new processes required for a successful ECRM implementation are not developed with the knowledge, help and acceptance of the employees who will be relied upon to use them, the project is doomed.[1]

ECRM OPPORTUNITIES

ECRM is to enhance its presenting opportunities to companies to improve their effectiveness and to deliver customer value. It can reduce the costs involved in communicating to customers, optimize work flows, facilitate better market segmentation and enable enhanced customer interactions, relationship and personalization opportunities.[4] ECRM can be used as an approach to relationship management with multiple stakeholders including customers, employees, channel partners and suppliers. Specific opportunities of ECRM highlighted here include enhanced customer interactions and relationships, managing customer touch points, personalization options and leveraging ECRM capabilities as a potential source of competitive advantage.

Enhanced Customer Interactions and Relationships

ECRM involves three phases, all of which are designed to manage the customer life cycle and maximize customer lifetime value: acquiring new customers, enhancing the profitability of existing customers and retaining profitable customers for life. All of these phases are dependent on the quality of customer information and insight available to the organization. By collecting information on-line the company has data that is already in a format to be pulled into its analytical processes without the steps of data entry.[4] Streamlining of the data collection process enhances information quality and timeliness. The company can also capture more information through the on-line channel leads to predict customer behavior, resulting in more targeted and customized relationship strategies. Through CRM the value of the relationship escalates for both parties: customers receive products and services more closely related to their needs, lifestyles and the organization cultivates a base of high-value, low-risk customers. The company which has recently adopted ECRM technology is the engineering division of ESB International (ESBIEFM). The company recognized that it required a better understanding of customers and their expectations in order to focus the organization's resources where they are most required. The business requirement for readily available real-time accurate information was identified as a priority. It was recognized and acknowledged that customer information and data acquired by customer-facing personnel and account managers should not reside with that person alone but should be a shared organizational asset available to relevant personnel within ESBIEFM and embedded within the company.

Managing Customer Touch Points

Customers are moving between traditional and online channels with greater frequency when dealing with organizations. ECRM systems support multichannel touch points with the company and a key challenge is providing a consistent experience for the customer. Offering multiple interaction paths scores convenience points for customers but this benefit quickly evaporates if the customers are forced to repeat themselves because one part of the organization is not synchronized with another. Customers accustomed to real time information and responses must be catered for when they switch to an alternative channel.[5] It shouldn't in principle make any difference whether a customer interacts with the company through the sales force, over the Web or indirectly through a reseller. For this reason effective multi-channel management has emerged as a successful CRM strategy within organizations.

Personalization and e-Loyalty

With ECRM technologies it becomes possible for a company to tailor the whole customer experience to the individual. Tailoring based on customer data, active personalization, includes information content presented, the products offered and also advertising from other organizations. The existence of direct-to-customer channels is the key enabler for automated systems to deliver highly relevant content because of the amount of data that can be collected. For example, every Amazon customer gets personal recommendations for books based on Amazon's personalization technology.[14]The personalized web pages of American Airlines have provided a source of competitive advantage in a fiercely competitive marketplace, as the Hertz Rent a Car strategy with its unique service for preferred customers. Through such personalized websites customers are empowered to customize the site to suit their preferences and facilitate their navigation.

Leveraging ECRM as a Source of Competitive Advantage

ECRM implementations are designed as a digital loyalty cycle that continuously improves to create lasting competitive advantage. When a company uses ECRM technology and redefines its business processes in customer acquisition and retention, it strengthens its capabilities in key areas that determine a customer's purchase decision including pricing, product quality, marketing, sales and customer service to create a virtuous digital loyalty cycle.[15] For example, eircom has adopted ECRM as a strategic imperative with net benefits for both the company and its customers. eircom's on-line sales and service channel, www.eircom.ie, was first developed as a high-level static marketing site in but since then has been upgraded to a fully integrated enterprise-scale portal application, incorporating a personalization platform and content management

system. The implementation of ECRM reduces the cost of communicating with customers and has led to reduced administrative and operational costs.

ECRM CHALLENGES

The ability to create intimacy with the customer is limited and building trust can be difficult. When managing an on-line channel companies are faced with the fact that greater choice creates fickleness among customers and with the competition only one click away there are no second chances to recover mistakes in these remote channels. Data integration and IT architecture challenges also exist for organizations adopting ECRM technologies.

Customer Interactions and Relationships

ECRM system enables traditional physical customer proximity to be substituted by digital proximity. The need for customer reassurance in the purchase decision can be exacerbated by new e-channels and needs to be addressed by the creation. Example: on-line communities, on-line shop assistants, customer testimonials and general reassurance about buying strategies and purchase choices for customers. Salmen and Muir promote the value of creating further contact possibilities between customers, in this case banking customers, within the context of virtual communities in which customer experiences can be exchanged.[10] The ability to create intimacy with the customer does not exist on-line and due to the remoteness of these channels building trust is more difficult, with the relationship element of ECRM harder to build beyond a purely transactional one. In the absence of such trust it is harder to get customers to share the data which is essential to creating effective CRM strategies.

Challenges of Data Integration and IT Architecture

An ECRM system is also highly dependent on neighboring systems to be effective, Example: traditional 'front office' CRM which has to be consistent with an ECRM system at both data and process levels, back office systems which supply product availability and pricing information as well as previous customer transaction details, an existing data consolidating customer related information and finally Web content management and authoring tools.[11] All of these linkages need to be effective and operational for ECRM to successfully impact company activities. This reinforces the need for companies to have well-developed business processes and information and technology infrastructures on which to build and sustain ECRM competences.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN CRM AND ECRM

ECRM provide customer with self-service browser based window to place orders, check order status, review purchase history request additional information about the product, send e-mails. The capabilities provide customers freedom in terms of place and time. The customer is no longer limited to contacting an organization during regular business hour and the organization does not have to provide a live contact for other end for customers enquires and requests. The users in CRM are the employees of the organization. The system provides access via set of predefined menus and choices, which cannot be customized by the user. Any customization requires making significant changes at the system level. On other hand, an individual can easily customize these applications and menus through their web based user interfaces by ECRM. In ECRM all applications are designed and implemented for web interaction and experience. Typically, the client does not need to download applets to access applications. The browser is the medium and it allows to access applications. It also allows to access appropriate information without any regard to platform of the client. From the customer perspective, it is just like accessing different Web Pages.

CRM IN DIFFERENT BUSINESS AREAS

Use Of CRM Strategy In Hotel Industry

The use of CRM strategy means different things for organizations in the hotel sector. In positioning on the market, hotels need to compete and develop their brand in order to attract and retain guests, and this requires flexibility of software capacities with the goal to respond to the requests in competitive market and changing conditions in industry.[7] CRM for hotels puts the customer in the center of business processes, the customer who is a part of living processes through which the company gains big competitive advantage. CRM allows efficient and measurable attracting of new guests and promotes loyalty and satisfaction

Use Of CRM Strategy In Banking And Insurance Sectors

Due to the highly competitive market in the banking sector, it is very difficult for banks to differentiate themselves from the competition because the services that they offer are very similar, which leaves the customer interaction as a way to distinguish the bank from the competition and the same goes for insurance companies. Customers usually choose a bank based on its location or how close it is to the customer's home or work place. Competitive pressure and dynamic market have contributed to the development of CRM in the financial sector. CRM solutions for Banking provide multi-channel communication with customers in a consistent and efficient manner. This distinguishes the bank from its competitors and provides the most efficient data collection, unified view of each client, enhanced decision making, product design and sales. Together this allows banks to know their clients and to make the most efficient use of customer interactions across multiple channels.[8] CRM solution also allows the increase of revenue through customized sales and customer service interactions, which allows banks to respond to new customers, products and markets faster and easier.

Use Of CRM Strategy In Higher Education

CRM solutions for higher education institutions make a fast, flexible and affordable solution that delivers a higher level of efficiency with tools that can help the university management to manage the daily activities and make well informed decisions. On the one hand, higher education CRM provides a clear and complete picture of each individual user (student) and all the activities the user performs within the institution. On the other hand, CRM allows students to carry out interactions with the university as a separate entity by providing a clear understanding of its statute within the organization.[9] For students this includes information on enrollment, registration, financial aid, student accounts and accommodation.

ANDROID CRM TOOL

Android is a mobile operating system based on the Linux kernel and currently developed by Google. With a user interface based on direct manipulation, Android is designed primarily for touchscreen mobile devices such as smartphones and tablet computers, with specialized user interfaces for televisions, cars, and wrist watches. The OS uses touch inputs that loosely correspond to real-world actions, like swiping, tapping, pinching, and reverse pinching to manipulate on-screen objects, and a virtual keyboard. Despite being primarily designed for touchscreen input, it has also been used in game consoles, digital cameras, regular PCs, and other electronics. [23]

ANDROID VERSIONS

Following are the versions of Google's Android operating system, which comes with a variety of Google applications. Unlike the iPhone, each Android device manufacturer can overlay its own user interface features, which means the same version of the OS may not function identically in different devices. In addition, OS versions are rolled out at different times, and not all Android devices qualify to receive new updates.

- Version 1.0/1.1 - September 2008

First version of Android released on the HTC G1. It included all the Google apps and synchronization (search, mail, contacts, calendar, etc.). In February 2009, Version 1.1 added the capability of saving attachments in messages.

- Cupcake 1.5 - April 2009

Support for Widgets, such as a search box into the app on the home screen, virtual keyboards, MPEG-4 video and YouTube/Picasa uploading.[25]

- Donut 1.6 - September 2009

Search expanded to include bookmarks and history. More camera integration and features.

- Eclair 2.0/2.1 - October 2009

Support for Microsoft Exchange mail. Search expanded to include SMS and MMS messages, and HTML5 support in the browser. More camera features, including flash, zoom and white balance.

- Froyo 2.2 - May 2010

Support for Bluetooth hands free, push notifications, Wi-Fi hotspot functionality and greater screen resolution. Better Microsoft Exchange and Android Market integration.

- Gingerbread 2.3 - December 2010

Introduced on the Samsung Galaxy Nexus S, support was added for VoIP, enhanced copy/paste, front-facing camera, AAC audio and near field communication (NFC). Gingerbread allowed for screens with WXGA and higher resolution.

- Honeycomb 3.0 - February 2011

Introduced on the Motorola Xoom, Honeycomb is a tablet-only version that takes advantage of larger screens. Touted as "3D Holographic," it adds toolbars at top and bottom and incorporates tabbed browsing and other desktop features. When plugging into a computer's USB port, Honeycomb uses Microsoft's Media Transfer Protocol for file transfer rather than connecting as a USB mass storage device.

- Ice Cream Sandwich 4.0 - October 2011

Introduced on Samsung's Galaxy Nexus, Ice Cream Sandwich (ICS) combines Gingerbread and Honeycomb versions into one. ICS added a raft of new features, including facial recognition unlocking, resizable Widgets, Wi-Fi Direct and touchscreen keys in lieu of hardware Home, Menu and Back buttons.

- Jelly Bean 4.1 - August 2012

Jelly Bean can provide the user with information automatically throughout the day. Also included are improved camera features and notifications. An internal "Project Butter" makes Android run a bit smoother, and the speech-to-text function works without an Internet connection, although not quite as accurately. Jelly Bean also includes an improved voice search, which is the counterpart to Apple's Siri.

- Jelly Bean 4.2 - November 2012

Major changes are support for multiple users on tablets, a panoramic photo mode and direct wireless transfer to a TV set via Miracast. Swiping gestures and predictive text were added to the keyboard.[26]

- Jelly Bean 4.3 - July 2013

Low-power Bluetooth Smart was added with improved support for right-to-left languages. Each tablet user can be restricted for parental control, store demos or other purposes. An autocomplete for the phone dialer offers numeric or name suggestions, and the OpenGL ES 3.0 graphics standard is supported for greater game realism.

- KitKat 4.4 (formerly Key Lime Pie) - October 2013

A slicker, more polished interface and a host of changes, including improvements for instant messaging, photo editing and a full-screen display mode that is more immersive. Support for older phones with less than 1GB of RAM memory. "OK Google" was added to activate a voice search.

- Lollipop 5.0 - December 2014

A redesigned user interface, known as Material Design, with notifications adhering to the card-based Google Now system. The Java Dalvik runtime engine is replaced by Android Runtime (ART), which provides cross-platform support for ARM, x86 and MIPS CPUs. Enterprise features include separating personal and business apps. Lollipop defaults to encrypting the user's data to prevent theft in the event the device is compromised. The user's passcode is required to unlock the device and data.[24]

CONCLUSION

ECRM has arrived and whether or not the name remains, the concept is here to stay. We have looked at the recent success of ECRM . We have addressed recent trends in the field, most notably the pairing of CI with ECRM solutions to gain a deeper understanding of the economics of customer behavior and value. We have also explored the kinds of problems that can accompany an ECRM implementation and how to avoid them. In addition, we have identified the critical issues that companies must consider at the threshold of ECRM implementation. Finally, we have examined Android as a CMR Tool.

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